

BEAT PLASTIC POLLUTION: INSTIL YOUNG MINDS WITH SUSTAINABLE PRACTICES AT THE SCHOOL LEVEL

Sharvari M Dicholkar

MSc Post Graduate IGNOU Student , Email Id: sharman1457276@gmail.com , Contact number -98020464971

Dr Mamata Tendulkar

Associate Professor , K. J. Somaiya College of Arts & Commerce (Autonomous), Vidyavihar – East, Mumbai-400077 Email:mamata.t@somaiya.edu Contact no. : - +919920291348

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Abstract

This study aims to increase awareness about plastic menace and hazards. It will raise awareness in the local community about plastic waste collection points and also its conversion to biodiesel. School children will be spokesperson to spread the awareness for a period of six months and more.

Theoretical Orientation: *To encourage everyone to refuse, reduce, reuse, recycle, and rethink their relationship with plastic, while also promoting systemic change.*

Methodology: *To combat the pervasive issue of plastic pollution that affects every corner of the planet. NGO like Athak Foundation along with School Leaders and Students (Nursery to Grade 10) will play a pivotal role to reduce plastic pollution.*

Main Results:

Masses will be aware about Plastic menace. There will be reduction in the amount of plastic use. Efforts will be made to ensure plastic is converted to usable fuel

Conclusions: *Beat Plastic Pollution, focusing on ending local plastic pollution through collective action, sustainable practices, and responsible conversion. This campaign highlights the widespread environmental and health impacts of plastic waste, from microplastics in the deepest oceans to human bodies, and encourages individuals, communities, NGOs and governments to find and implement solutions.*

Keywords: *PlasticMenace , Sustainable Goals, RecyclingTechnologies, Collaboration ,Collective Action.*

Introduction

We human beings are a part of ecosystem which is made up of biotic and abiotic components. In our highly populated country, our actions have contributed to large waste in the surroundings of which we should take responsibility to clean the same.

We are responsible for different types of waste. But here we are largely talking about only plastic waste.[1][2]

One small step this year taken is the help our Mother Earth be free of plastic waste and reduce the impact of plastic pollution in line with our theme for the World Environment Day: Beat Plastic Pollution’.

We all are aware that the repercussions of plastic pollution extend beyond mere inconvenience, manifesting in tangible impacts on public health, well-being, and the environment. [3]

The first step to address the multifaceted challenge of plastic pollution is to create awareness among the public. Here it is important to note that we are sensitising our youth today about generation of plastic waste, its hazards and recycling plastic, reducing its use.

The school: New Horizon Scholars School, Airoli invited members of NGO-Athak Foundation, to conduct an awareness program in line with reducing plastic waste and convert it. They spoke to grades: Grade 5 and Grade 8 on the theme beat plastic pollution.

They gave examples of how marine life is impacted.[4]

Their shared the below information which also convinced the students about immediate action required.

The chemical structure of most plastics renders them resistant to many natural processes of degradation and as a result they are slow to degrade.^[5] Together, these factors allow large volumes of plastic to enter the environment as mismanaged waste which persists in the ecosystem and travels throughout food webs.

Plastic pollution can afflict land, waterways and oceans. It is estimated that 1.1 to 8.8 million tonnes of plastic waste enters the ocean from coastal communities each year.^[8]

In this study students take responsibility to reduce plastic use and spread this knowledge with peers and adults. The youth today is becoming aware at an early age and moving ahead responsibly.

This plastic waste collection is conducted once a month consistently. The waste is collected by Athak team (NGO), they then convert it to high-speed diesel at Athak's affiliate in Pune .

Objectives:

To bring about slow and systemic change in the environment. To reduce plastic waste. We were able to collect around 10kg of plastic so far. We would propose to target reduction of 100kg plastic waste. Sustainable products and its use will be encouraged to have a sustainable living lifestyle. Youth are mouldable and will bring about a change when spoken at an early age. They are given opportunity to be spokesperson as plastic warriors.

Methodology:

In the academic year 2025-26, members of Athak foundation spoke to grades: Grade 5 and Grade 8 on the theme beat plastic pollution. They spoke about plastic waste generated and its menace caused. They informed the students about small steps that they can take to reduce plastic.

They were also made aware about the practices undertaken by the Athak Foundation in collecting of the plastic waste on monthly basis consistently and recycling it to bio-diesel at their Pune plant.

The students of age group 9 years till age of 16years is given a platform to speak to a larger audience during meetings once in three months. The adults are also made aware about plastic and its impact. They are also given information about how to manage the waste and also minimise the waste at the individual level.

This information was then disseminated by the recipient students to others. The school and its management are supportive in helping to save our environment

The school spreads awareness monthly about collection drive of the plastic waste by the NGO via messaging to spread it to large audience.

The steps taken are consistent and impactful in spreading awareness about plastic waste, its collection and reducing its use mindfully.

Observations:

Few observations seen after the study are as follows:

1. Students were aware about plastic waste and its impact on the environment.
2. Students approach was positive in bringing about change in reducing the plastic waste.
3. Local community was inspired to participate in actions to reduce the plastic waste.
4. School stakeholders are having a common mission to help reduce plastic waste.
5. School and Management is very proactive in the vision to see minimum plastic usage and recycle plastic waste

Results and Discussions:

Beat Plastic Pollution is a responsibility of every individual to live in a sustainable ecosystem. This method of creating awareness has helped reduce the use of plastic by many.

We were able to collect around 10kg of plastic so far. We would propose to target reduction of 100kg plastic waste this year. We are finding alternative to use of plastic and use of sustainable products like cloth and paper is given more importance.

The awareness has spread to more than 600 individuals so far. The target is to reach double the audience this year.

Also a step to visit the Pune plant can be thought of and arranged in the near future to see the conversion of plastic waste into bio-diesel.

Conclusions:

The study has sensitized youth of the country about plastic pollution and its impact. The method so far has been successful and received great feedback by the adults when they see young children aware and have knowledge to contribute to the society.

Small baby steps are taken at the local level to BEAT PLASTIC POLLUTION: INSTIL YOUNG MINDS WITH SUSTAINABLE PRACTICES AT THE SCHOOL LEVEL.

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